

IMPACT OF 3D DEVELOPMENT ON THE ECONOMY

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Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda ko'pchilik qo'shimchalar texnologiyalarining hozirgi rivojlanish bosqichini shaxsiy kompyuterlarning birinchi modellari bozori paydo bo'lgan davr bilan haqli ravishda taqqoslaydi. O'sha paytda kompyuterlarning afzalliklari kam odam uchun juda ravshan bo'lib tuyuldi, ammo o'n yildan kamroq vaqt ichida raqamli texnologiyalar oddiy odamlarning hayotini soddalashtirib, biznes uchun yangi bozorlarni yaratib, dunyoni o'zgartirishga muvaffaq bo'ldi.

Аннотация: Сегодня многие справедливо сравнивают нынешний этап развития аддитивных технологий с периодом, когда на рынке появились первые модели персональных компьютеров. В то время преимущества компьютеров мало кому казались совершенно очевидными, но менее чем за десятилетие цифровым технологиям удалось перевернуть мир, упростив жизнь обычных людей и создав новые рынки для бизнеса.

Annotation: Today many people rightly compare the current stage of development of additive technologies with the period when the market for the first models of personal computers appeared. At that time, the benefits of computers seemed quite obvious to few, but in less than a decade, digital technologies managed to turn the world around, simplifying the lives of ordinary people and creating new markets for business.

Калит сўзлар: 3Д босиб чиқариш, 3Д printer, 3Д сканерлаш, қўшимчалар ишлаб чиқариш технологиялари, 3Д model, ишлаб чиқариш, иқтисодий самарадорлик.

Ключевые слова: 3D-печать, 3D-принтер, 3D-сканирование, аддитивные технологии производства, 3D-модель, производство, экономическая эффективность,

Keywords: 3D printing, 3D printer, 3D scanning, additive manufacturing technologies, 3D model, production, economic efficiency

Today, 3D printing or "additive manufacturing" is no longer a distant future, but a reality. Over the past 10 years, this method of production has given impetus to the development of new developments in many areas: architecture, design, construction, automotive, space and military industries, medicine, light and jewelry industries, education, etc. 3D printing allows you to make a product based on an information

model. In the end, you get a product that is not inferior in quality to a product produced using traditional technology [1].

Additive technologies will not replace traditional mass production, market participants agree. But there is no doubt that 3D printing can be effectively integrated into the production processes of many industrial companies and bring them tangible benefits.

Despite the significant advantages, the 3D industry faces a number of challenges. One of them is the need for investments in infrastructure and technology, which can be expensive and take time to pay off. In addition, some countries may lack specialists in the field of 3D technology, which may slow down the implementation of the technology. However, with the development of 3D education and the increased availability of 3D equipment, these challenges can be overcome.

Businesses that need to take into account the unique characteristics of each customer and ensure product personalization have already adopted additive technologies. They are used in dentistry, orthopedics, jewelry for the production of single products of a specific configuration. This property of 3D printing has also been adopted by enterprises from the automotive industry, shipbuilding, aerospace, instrumentation, nuclear industry and defense industry. They resort to the help of additive technologies when it is necessary to design and produce a more complex product with a lower cost of development and production, to do it quickly and efficiently [2].

A car from a 3D printer. The automotive industry has long used 3D printing to create prototypes, as well as complex parts, tooling and decor. Some manufacturers (Daihatsu, Mini) offer to customize the car using printed decorative elements and interior details. There are single cars and concept maps completely printed on a 3D printer.

Due to the lack of standards and technical requirements for products manufactured using 3D technologies, manufacturers, depending on the industry, have to confirm

compliance with the standards of equipment, technologies, materials, personnel, and individual components. Some industries, such as aerospace, nuclear, and healthcare, require the use of certified materials or a special assessment of their quality. The lack of a generally accepted standardization system complicates these processes, which significantly slows down the spread of additive technologies in industry. The technology developed more than 30 years ago. [3].

3D printing, despite regulatory and economic barriers, is already being implemented in manufacturing enterprises. It is difficult to imagine the aerospace, aviation, automotive, and defense industries without it, where unique shapes and special properties of parts are important. There is an increasing interest in additive technologies in other areas where technology helps to solve not only engineering, but also commercial tasks.

There are several development paths that are initiated precisely by the demand of the market:

1. Universal photopolymers for printing models for further mold removal;
2. Photopolymers with low ash content for precision industrial casting of metals into moldable molds;
3. Highly filled composite materials for 3D-photo printing;
4. Synthesized materials for photo printing;
5. Materials for printing enclosures for custom wearable and installable electronics, prototypes and enclosures for low-volume products;
6. Biocompatible, bio-substitutable and biodegradable materials for medical use, All materials from this list are sharpened for a small batch or full capacity [4].

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